

turned into the color of clotted blood. Rice varieties could not be graded on panicle infection.

Germination and seedling vigor of discolored and healthy grains of 4 selected varieties were tested in petri plates at 30± 1°C. Varieties differed in reduction of percent germination and

root and shoot length (Table 1). Reduction was maximum in RP2151-76-1 and minimum in RP2151-27-1. Although germination in discolored seeds of Palman 579 was not affected, root length reduction was noticed.

Affected and healthy panicles from six plots of Jaya and Pusa 2-21 were

collected to study the effect of SBL on yield parameters. Number of filled grains was reduced and number of unfilled and discolored grains was higher in affected panicles (Table 2). Infection was more pronounced on Pusa 2-21 than on Jaya. □

Effect of *Azolla bipinnata* soil amendment on reduction in viability of sclerotia of rice stem rot (SR) fungus

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A greenhouse pot experiment examined the effect of *Azolla bipinnata* used as an organic substrate on the survival of sclerotia of the SR fungus *Sclerotium oryzae*. Soil artificially infested with sclerotia of *S. oryzae* at 5 sclerotia/g of soil was amended with fresh azolla at 0, 0.1, 0.5, and 1% wt/ wt. The soil in 7-cm-diameter pots was adjusted and maintained at 50, 75, and 100% moisture-holding capacity by watering daily. At 0, 10-, 20-, 40-, and 80-d intervals, sclerotia were separated by wet sieving and their viability tested on water agar supplemented with streptomycin sulfate and penicillin at

Table 1. Reduction in viability of sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae* in soil amended with *Azolla bipinnata* at different moisture levels. Karachi, Pakistan.

Azolla treatment	Moisture (%)	Reduction in viability ^a (%)			
		10 d	20 d	40 d	80 d
Control	50	4	3	3	0
	75	5	4	8	4
	100	0	10	13	13
Azolla 0.1%	50	10	3	9	5
	75	0	14	8	13
	100	14	13	4	17
Azolla 0.5%	50	4	12	8	25
	75	12	0	13	14
	100	5	8	17	35
Azolla 1.0%	50	1	18	5	29
	75	13	8	13	18
	100	12	16	14	26

^a Zero reduction at 0 d.

Table 2. Analysis of variance for the viability of sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae*.

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F ratio
Treatments (T)	1045.511	3	348.50	3.82**
Moisture (M)	625.328	2	312.69	3.43*
Time (D)	4220.755	4	1055.19	11.58**
TXM	306.911	6	51.15	0.56
TXD	1152.045	12	96.00	1.05
MXD	670.128	8	83.77	0.92
TXMXD	1853.533	24	77.23	0.85
Residual	10938.667	120	91.15	
Total	20812.978	179		

*P<0.05

**P<0.01

3,000 ppm each.

Maximum reduction, up to 35%, in sclerotial viability was observed with azolla at 0.5% wt/ wt (Table 1).

Azolla at different concentrations and at different time intervals showed significant reduction in viability of sclerotia (Table 2). Moisture also was significant. Interactions among

amendment, moisture, and time were not significant. Presumably soil incorporation of azolla and the decomposition of organic matter generate anaerobic conditions and/ or accumulation of fungitoxic substances due to increased microbial activity, resulting in a reduction in viability of *S. oryzae* sclerotia. □

Pestalotia oryzae - a new rice fungus in India

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A severe glume spot disease of rice was found in Manipur for the first time in 1985-86.

Symptoms appeared first as small, pale brown spots which gradually increased to 2 mm in size. The center of the spot is gray-brown with a dark brown margin and bears minute fruiting bodies of the fungus.

Diseased grains were collected in separate bags from different rice-growing valley areas during the crop season. The causal organism was isolated and maintained on potato

Panicle stage and susceptibility to *Pestalotia oryzae*. Iroisemba, Manipur, India, 1985-86.

Panicle stage	Panicles inoculated (no.)	Panicles infected (no.)
Just emerged	30	2
Milk	30	30
Dough	30	6
Mature	30	0

dextrose agar (PDA) medium. Pathogenicity of the fungus was proved by inoculating young panicles with 7-d-old cultures.

The fungus failed to infect the living leaves. However, it could easily infect dead rice leaves.

The isolated pathogenic fungus has been identified as *Pestalotia oryzae* Hara. This is the first record of its